

Study on Customer's Satisfaction Towards Green Remit Card users of SBI at Kaveripattinam Branch

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Abstract

The present study focuses on the utilization of card holders towards green remit card. The study was designed to gain a better understanding of the factors influencing utilization and satisfaction of card holders. The study also analyses the extent of satisfaction of green remit card by card holders and the level of awareness, services and perception of card holders. The study could be beneficiary to both the banker and the customers. Form this study the preference and problems of the customer can be study and offer suitable suggestions based on the result of the study.

Introduction

Green remit card/green channel counter (our green initiatives for an environment friendly banking) facilitates faster deposit/withdrawal and eliminates the need of manual forms. However, you may also deposit cash as permitted without GREEN REMIT CARD.

SBI green remit card is a simple magstripe based card without PIN. After the initiative of digital India, cash transactions are mostly avoided. Green card helps in reducing paper work as it is linked to a specific account only to which you can deposit the money you don't have to fill any receipts. Just visit the counter or cash deposit machine, swipe your card enter amount deposit the amount. It is that simple. It is felt by that bank that customers should use these technologies and move towards green India. It is not compulsory but to change habits we have to be forced to accept change.

Review of Litreature

Dr. Arvind A. Dhond (2013), conducted study titled "An empirical study on green channel counter in banks". The researcher identified some problem faced by the customers and banks, he gives solution that the green channel counter helps to solve the problems.

Moorthy and pradeepa (2014), conducted study on customer satisfaction towards SBI green remit card- an empirical study, they opined that banking sectors played an active role in the economic development of the country. The green channel counter is functioning in all branches of state bank of India. The new technologies help the banks to reduce the work load. They are ready to use such facility

because they can save their time and money of personal visit to branch. The green channel counters help the customers to have convenient and comfortable banking transactions.

Vijayasarithi and velmurugan (2015) In banking the most important operation like cash deposit, cash withdrawal and inter banking transfer can be done by the way of writing channels and using cheque leaves. The banks have implemented the certain technology services to cut down the usage of more paperwork and reduce transaction cost. Green remit card avoids as much paper work in their banking transaction. The green remit card helps the customers to have convenient and comfortable banking transactions.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the satisfaction level of customers using by SBI green remit card system.
2. To identify the factors that influences the customer satisfaction of SBI green remit card.
3. To study the level of understanding about the areas for green remit card system among The SBI customers.

Scope of the Study

1. The present study focuses on the utilization of card holders towards green remit card.
2. The study was designed to gain a better understanding of the factors influencing utilization and satisfaction of card holders.
3. The study also analyses the extent of satisfaction of green remit card by card holders and the level of awareness, services and perception of card holders.

Research Methodology

Type of Research

The research was descriptive research.

Source of Data

1. Primary data
2. Secondary data

Primary data

The primary data are those which are collected for first time and information that a researcher should top way with his interest and types source.

Secondary data

Secondary data consist of information that already exists somewhere, which has been collected for specific purpose in this study. The secondary data for this study was collected from various books, websites, journals, magazines and organization brochures.

Sampling Design

Convenience sampling is used for collection of data by the researcher from the respondents in the premises of krishnagiri.

Sampling Size

In this study sample size made as 66 based on convenience sampling.

Data Analysis and Interpretation**Table Gender of the Respondents**

S.No	Gender	No.of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Male	38	57
2	Female	28	43
Total		66	100

Source: Primary Data**Interpretation**

From the above table 1 shows that the gender of the respondent, out of 66 respondents, 57% of the respondents are male, and remaining 43% of the respondents are female. Majority (57%) of the respondents are male.

Table Age Group of the Respondents

S.No	Age group	No.of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Below 30 years	24	36
2	31-40 years	26	40
3	41-50 years	11	16
4	Above 50 years	5	8
Total		66	100

Source: Primary Data**Interpretation**

From the above table 2 clear that the age group of the respondents, among the 66 respondents, 40% of the respondents are belonged to the age group of between 31-40 years, 36% of the respondents are belonged to the age group of between 20-30 years, 16% of the respondents are belonged to the age group of between 41-50 years, 8% of the respondents are belonged to the age group of above 50 years. Majority (40%) of the respondents are belonged to the age group between 31-40 years.

Table Level of Satisfaction Towards SBI Green Remit Card Services

S.No	Level of Satisfaction	No.of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Highly satisfied	8	13
2	Satisfied	48	71
3	Dissatisfied	6	10
4	Highly dissatisfied	4	6
Total		66	100

Source: Primary Data**Interpretation**

From the above table 3 shows that the respondents level of satisfaction towards green remit card services, out of 66 respondents, 71% of the respondents are satisfied for the green remit card service, 13% of the respondents are highly satisfied for the green remit card service, 10% of the respondents are dissatisfied for the green remit card service, 6% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied for the green remit card service. Majority (71%) of the respondents are satisfied for the green remit card services.

Findings

1. Majority (57%) of the respondents are male.
2. Majority (40%) of the respondents are belonged to the age group between 31-40 years.
3. Majority (71%) of the respondents are green remit card is important in the technical world.

Suggestions

4. Agriculture people are interested to utilize more green remit card services.
5. SBI should adopt go green remit card by this method bank could reduce the carbon footprint from the environment.
6. To improve the usage of green remit card is necessary in the generation.

Conclusion

For effective green remit card, the RBI and the Indian government should play a pro active role and formulate green policy guidelines and financial incentives. This initiative save more papers, reduce work burden and transaction cost. This system was mainly introduced to avoid the token system and waiting in queue. Using this system customer can directly go to the counter, at the time of customers to feel no pin number to green remit card. So alternate solution for providing the pin number for green remit card users. This system is more helpful to the customers, to do the banking transaction at easy.

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